

Collaborative Teaching Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in the Municipality of Malasiqui

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of practice of the collaborative teaching strategy used by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the Municipality of Malasiqui Schools Division Office I Pangasinan. This study used the descriptive method of research to ascertain the utilization of the partnership teaching strategies. The sources of data will be taken from the analysis of the responses of the teachers from the given questionnaire. In this research, the instruments that allow the investigator to generate the required data and specifics will be crucial. Since this research is descriptive in nature, it will detail current circumstances and conditions pertaining to the study, which comprised 80 teacher respondents in total. The validated questionnaire provided the necessary information to assess the degree of partnership teaching strategy implementation. The results of this investigation were molded by a careful analysis of the participants' responses. The researcher was able to determine the efficacy of the TLE teachers' partnership teaching practices following the data collection. The noticeable findings of the study are as follows: Respondents of this investigation are 80 Technology and Livelihood Education teachers who are randomly selected from the Municipality of Malasiqui in the Schools Division Office I of Pangasinan. Data revealed that 33 of the respondents coming from the total of 80 are MA Degree unit holders, 67 are TLE majors, 26 are of 11-15 years of teaching experience, and 36 of them attended regional trainings. The level of practiced of using the partnership teaching strategy by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers is described as "Moderately Practiced" which means, TLE teachers are using the partnership teaching strategies which is a necessary tool in helping and improving the academic performance of the learners as well as the teaching performance of the teachers. The problems encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the implementation of partnership teaching strategy is described as "Moderately Serious". There is no significant relationship between the problems encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the implementation of partnership teaching strategies and their profile variables. Moreover, in the field of specialization garnered a significance of 0.73, therefore the null hypothesis should be accepted. It implies that the level of practiced in partnership teaching strategies of teachers is not dependent on their field of specialization. There is a significant relationship between the Practiced partnership teaching strategies and the problems encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the implementation. The level of performance of the Grade 8 learners was described as mastered, an indication of an effective used of the strategy. A development plan was proposed to help to address problems of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the adoption and familiarization of the collaborative teaching strategy.

Chapter 1

The Problem

Rationale: In the light of the ongoing changes that are taking place in the educational landscape, collaborative teaching is becoming a potent instrument to satisfy the diverse demands of teachers and students. Embedded on diversity, collaboration, and a shared body of knowledge, this pedagogical approach could empower passive classrooms into dynamic learning spaces. This inquiry will critically review the

different types of collaborative teaching, their application, advantages, limitations, and implications for the future of education.

The old instruction paradigm is being displaced today by innovative approaches under which educators collaborate and pool their collective experience. Collaborative learning is one such groundbreaking technique. Under this cooperative pedagogical paradigm, teachers from diverse backgrounds pool their collective experience and engage in the collaborative development of teaching. Teaching in collaboratives offers several important benefits. Collaborative teaching was found to enhance the academic performance, engagement, and social interactions of the students (Cook & Friend, 2009). In addition, it would provide a networked arsenal for tools for curriculum creation, problem-solving, and effective classroom management for the educators. Collaborative teaching is an approach that could be embraced by educational institutions to promote an innovative and collaborative culture. It would mean adapting the teaching strategies to the demands of 21st-century learning.

Collaborative teaching utilizes several collaborative or cooperative teaching methods, and these are tailored to suit the unique needs of both the teachers and students. For example, inclusion collaborative teaching (Villa & Thousand, 2017) focuses on offering students with a wide range of abilities equivalent educational opportunities, and interdisciplinary collaborative teaching (Cook & Friend, 2009), where educators from different disciplines work in tandem to design lessons that are more integrated. The teacher observes each other's teaching techniques and learns from them, and this form of peer collaborative teaching supports sustained professional development (Friend, 2014). While contributing positively to the learning environment for the students, these forms of teaching also offer teachers opportunities to perfect their pedagogical styles and broaden their pedagogical portfolios.

In line with this, in the field of Mathematics, the method of teaching and learning in classrooms must vary from only explaining mathematics to teaching the same subject using a variety of tactics and approaches in order to reach the aim of teaching and learning. Research has been done both locally and globally to determine the best methods and strategies to use in schools. The cooperative learning method was created as a result. Cooperative learning is a teaching approach that concentrates on the students and has them complete tasks in groups. In order to achieve both their own and their groupmates' learning objectives, group members will interact with one another (Felder & Brent, 2007; Li, 2013; McCafferty, Jacobs & Iddings (2006).

Technical vocational education (TVE) for Senior High School, often referred to as Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) for Junior High School, is an essential facet of education that focuses on equipping students with real-world knowledge and skills relating to specific industries and occupations.

Studies in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) equip students with practical skills that may be applied right away to a wide range of industries and professions, increasing their employability. The study by Ramos and Vicente (2020) reveals how TLE equips students with useful abilities that employers value, enhancing their employment opportunities and career prospects.

TLE education typically places an emphasis on business and entrepreneurial skills in order to prepare students to become future entrepreneurs and business leaders. The research by Tumlos and Pontillas (2018) demonstrates how TLE promotes an entrepreneurial mindset and set of abilities, which aids the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and local economies.

As an effective way of ensuring that standards for academics are improved, Collaborative teaching, also referred to as collaborative teaching or co-teaching is being embraced. It has been underlined by scholars as being critical in the facilitation of inclusion, realization of the diversity of students' needs as learners, and in developing a sense of belonging in them (Smith & Cook, 2020; Friend & Cook, 2007). A full learning experience is achieved when instructors have diverse backgrounds and skills besides different perspectives that interact to produce a harmonious atmosphere. In such working relations, each member contributes special skills to it. Collaborative teaching creates a harmonious and active class environment that allows development of critical thinking skills as well as in-depth knowledge of the topics under discussion since the process involves joint planning, instructional strategies, and assessment methods.

In Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), Collaborative teaching is crucial for raising academic standards and preparing students for issues they may encounter in the real world. Students may benefit from more thorough and useful learning experiences as a result of collaboration between educational institutions, corporate partners, and other stakeholders. By bridging the gap between academic comprehension and

practical application, this method gives students the knowledge and skills they need to succeed in their future careers.

The other advantage is that it promotes the strong interaction between academia and business. Students gain knowledge of the current market trends, technological developments, and practical applications by working on various projects with professionals and experts from different fields. According to a study by Catelo, D. T. (2016), "this practice enables instructors to modify their curriculum to fit the demand in the market and therefore students graduate, not as just an extra number but with the current relevant skills of service delivery".

With the help of Collaboratives, students can experience practicum learning. The industry partners of the institution may give students resources such as workshops, internships, and mentorship programs, among others; to help them deal with actual projects that can prepare and equip them with valuable business experience. As discussed in a related article by Crisostomo, M. A., 2019 this active learning practice encourages students in how to solve problems and think critically.

Moreover, cooperative learning (CL) requires students to work together and learn as a group. They must be accountable for both their own education and their friends' educations as well. By rewarding or recognizing participation, cooperative learning aims to make learning enjoyable for the students. Cooperative learning also inspires students.

Based on the explanation given by Juriah Long (2010), cooperative learning in a way modifies the traditional approach by developing the higher order thinking skills of students. To explain further, Juriah Long (2010) states that in the case of understanding the concepts that are related to the topic that is being taught, students are required to express their views and opinions and this also helps the students develop their self-confidence and learning performance indirectly.

Throughout the years, teaching has never ceased to bring in new ideas and methods that might help improve student learning and performance. And one of the many ways that are commonly utilized to express ideas and thoughts is Collaborative teaching.

Moreover, one of the distinctive features of Collaborative teaching is more than just forming teams or groups for the students, is what cooperative learning practices are all about. In this teaching process, students work together to achieve a specific learning goal (Johnson & Johnson, 2000). The instructor may have a particular learning objective for the students and, in this regard, they come together to achieve the learning goal by exchanging ideas, helping each other understand the topic, and coming up with alternative explanations and examples which will support the learning goal of his or her team. This instructional strategy has successfully been used in a range of learning environments and disciplines. Researchers have found that through the use of the cooperative learning strategy in the classroom, learners were able to develop intellectually, socially, and emotionally (Sadker & Sadker, 2000). Academic achievement, interpersonal relationships within the group, and self-esteem were enhanced.

Shimazoe and Aldrich (2010) also note that employing a Collaborative teaching or cooperative learning technique with students has a number of benefits. Cooperative learning promotes thorough subject retention, to start. Second, students perform better in cooperative learning than in competitive or solo learning. Thirdly, learners learn social and civic virtues. Fourthly, they improve their capacity for higher-order, analytical thinking. Fifth, group learning encourages personal growth. Finally, students develop positive views of independent learning.

Numerous studies have demonstrated the positive effects of Collaborative and cooperative learning on academic achievement, long-term memory, attitudes toward mathematics, self-concept, and social abilities. There should be more possibilities for peer collaboration, issue solving, and discussion. Studies employing cooperative learning were undertaken by several math educators and found to boost student math achievement (Brush, 1997; Isik and Tarim, 2009; Nichols and Miller, 1994; Tarim, 2009; Tarim and Akdeniz, 2008).

The researcher come up with the study on determining the effectiveness of Collaborative teaching strategies in improving the academic performance of Grade 8 learners as variables in the study at the Municipality of Malasiqui. The researcher would like to introduce some of the Collaborative techniques and strategies in order to at least address the learning losses caused by pandemic. Most importantly, Technology and Livelihood Education as a subject covers the huge amount of percentage in measuring their academic

performance. She believes on the positive impact of this research study in order to create patterned and well-crafted curriculum for further reference in the near future.

As teacher in this subject that students are most likely to despise, we must recognize and identify the best teaching strategies for our learners in order to maintain their attention, learning, and enjoyment at the same time knowing which of the several ways the learners are most at ease is helpful. This led the researcher to conduct a study on Collaborative teaching strategy that might enhance students' work-related skills and knowledge for learners.

Theoretical Framework: The researcher presented and lists theories that are logically relevant to the topic of the investigation. Researchers in the field who have conducted other studies that are regarded to be connected to this topic have supported the theories advanced here.

The **theory of collaborative learning** highlights the significance of interpersonal interaction and group engagement in the learning process. It holds that students scaffold each other's knowledge creation and understanding in their zones of proximal development, leading to increased understanding and knowledge. It was developed by Lev Vygotsky. Activities in this category that lead to active participation, a variety of opinions, and the creation of critical thinking skills include group discussions, peer teaching, and cooperative projects. Such interactions create the opportunity for students to work on difficult topics, advance their ideas, and improve their capabilities for problem solving, thus increasing learning.

The **Social Interdependence Theory** by Johnson & Johnson emphasizes the benefits of cooperative relationships for academic success. This hypothesis claims that people are more likely to collaborate, pool resources, and help each other to achieve common goals when they feel their success is correlated with the achievement of their peers. According to the theory, there exist four types of interdependence: cooperative, competitive, negative, and positive. By inducing learning conditions that lead to constructive interdependence, educators are able to create a sense of shared responsibility, progress in the effectiveness of communication, and improvement in quality learning.

Therefore, according to the **constructivist learning theory**, the learner actually actively constructs their knowledge by integrating new information into their pre-existing mental models. The theory can be traced to the works of Piaget and Bruner. Central to the approach is the role of prior knowledge and cultural background in the social world in relation to the process of learning. Students enhance their cognitive development and knowledge level through concrete activities, discussions, and problem-solving exercises. This active knowledge-building approach encourages the learner to be independent, think critically, and understand the subject much better.

Peer collaboration is one component of **Peer-Assisted Learning Strategies (PALS)**, developed by Fuchs and Fuchs, a research-based teaching approach applied to improve learning. Within this context of PALS, the members constantly switch roles through controlled dyadic interaction, alternating between the roles of tutor and tutee. The tutor explains to the tutee, providing feedback and explanations to the tutee to better understand content and to assist them in the accomplishment of work on their academic assignments. This style of collaborative teaching improves the development of healthy social networks, self-assuredness, and academic performance with students.

Reciprocal teaching is a comprehension strategy developed by Palincsar and Brown that progresses reading skills with the aid of cooperative dialogue. With this strategy, students take on the leadership roles of summarizer, questioner, clarifier, and predictor by engaging in conversation about a text. What students get from it is even further development of their critical thinking and metacognitive knowledge, through active engagement with the material, sharing their points of view, and working collaboratively with others to get through tough parts. Reciprocal teaching gives the tools to students that build meaning, confirm understanding, and eventually develop as readers.

Conceptual Framework: The Philippine government has provided the Department of Education (DepEd) with mandates by virtue of Republic Act 9155, also known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001. This is supposed to manage basic education in kindergarten to Grade 12 for both public and private schools and learning centers, ensure access, equity, and quality education, as well as meet the learning demands and needs of every Filipino.

The grounding of shared responsibilities and innovative pedagogies for collaborative teaching rests on several pieces of legislation and policy frameworks. Significant among them is the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013," otherwise referred to as Republic Act No. 10533, and the grounding legislation of the K–12 curriculum. This law focuses on the actual adoption of the numerous teaching methodologies, including collaborative teaching, in order to make the environment for learning enriched and make sure that the learners leave the facility well-rounded. RA 10533, 2013, through the K–12 curriculum, promotes collaboration among teachers in designing and implementing lessons so that it offers a more holistic and integrated way of learning to the students.

DepEd Order number 29 series 2017 – Policy Guidelines on System Assessment in the K To 12 Basic Education Program, this specific order of the department articulates the bases of grading learners and determining the achievement level of each learner using the different teacher's strategy and approaches.

According to **DepEd Order 31 series of 2012** for grades 7 through 10, a separate period for independent/cooperative learning that lasts two to four hours per week may be added to the time allotted for classes in order to give students the option of learning certain topics, content, or procedures on their own or with others. Schools may want to consider offering a separate period for independent and cooperative learning for classes that would benefit the most from this type of class programming (in other words, in addition to their use by teachers as a teaching strategy or instructional activity).

Statement of the Problem: This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of collaborative teaching strategies in the teaching of Technology and Livelihood Education in the Municipality of Malasiqui for the School Year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the profile of the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 Highest Educational Attainment;
 - 1.2 Field of Specialization;
 - 1.3 Length of experience as TLE Teacher; and
 - 1.4 Relevant trainings attended in TLE?
2. What is the level of practice of the different collaborative teaching strategies utilized by the TLE teachers?
3. Is there a significant relationship between level of practice and profile of teachers?

4. What are the problems encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the implementation of Collaborative teaching strategy?
5. What is the level of performance of the Grade 8 learners in TLE according to the Collaborative teaching strategy used by the teacher?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of practice of collaborative teaching strategies and student performance?
7. Based from the findings, a development plan will be proposed to help to address problems of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the adoption and familiarization of the Collaborative teaching strategy.

Assumption: The following research hypotheses in their null were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between the profile variable of teachers and the level of practice of collaborative teaching strategies.
2. There is no significant difference between the level of practice of collaborative teaching strategies and the level of performance of the grade 8 learners.

Scope and Delimitation : This study was conducted in the Municipality of Malasiqui comprises of the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers, Schools Division Office I of Pangasinan, during the school year 2023 – 2024.

The variables that were investigated in this study focused on determining the profile of the teacher-respondents, level of practiced of the Collaborative teaching strategies, determining the significant difference and significant relationship of the problems encountered across profile variable, designing and proposing of Collaborative teaching strategies for Technology and Livelihood Education, determining the level of performance of the learners and identification of the different problems encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the implementation of Collaborative teaching strategy and the formulation of development plan to address problems, adoption and familiarization of the Collaborative teaching strategies designed to improve the performance of the learners.

Significance of the Study: Adequate instructional materials as well as the systematic implementation will help learners develop habits of mind that allow them to view the world through a critical scope. Repeated learner exposure to critical thinking practices will assist learners in all academic disciplines, as well as translate to life beyond high school.

Thus, this study will prove to be beneficial to the following:

- **Learners.** The learners are the most significant aspect in the learning experience, the findings and observations generated in this study will serve as a guide to their own technological learning. These will be of tremendous assistance and additional knowledge to students, which they can use into their future jobs as they will take part in the world of work.
- **Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers.** A teacher's function in the classroom is to be a catalyst, facilitator, monitor, and evaluator of the students' learning. Teachers must be aware of how their students perform, participate, and behave in class. It is critical that teachers analyze this study in order to guide learners; additionally, teacher teaching may enhance upholding this information. Teachers may need to incorporate the knowledge gained from this study into the classroom.
- **Curriculum Planner.** The result of the study can be used in planning and establishing significant activities for the effective Technology and Livelihood Education instruction.
- **School Administrators.** The findings of this study will serve as a call to action for administrators in terms of effective planning, direction, or guidance by encouraging instructors to utilize more applicable, appropriate, and effective methods and strategies that will improve their teaching abilities and performance. They may profit from this study because it will enlighten them on some strategies for enhancing their facilities and putting the proposed remedial efforts into action.
- **Parents.** Results of this study may provide parents feedback on the nature of the classroom performance of their children through their teachers who may offer some ways for children to strive more on their Technology and Livelihood Education subject.

- **Guidance Counselors.** They will also be aided from this study by means of supplying those steadfast data of the verdicts for analysis and for guidance purposes especially in choosing the career path for learners.
- **Researcher.** The results of the study would provide meaningful experience and insights in gathering and organizing data as well as for the improvement of teaching – learning process.
- **Future Researchers.** The results of this investigation can be used as a tool or guide for the future researchers also from to conduct a study similar to the present research investigation.

Definition of Terms: To better understand the study and have a clear grasp of the terms used, the following terms are operationally defined.

- **Academic Performance.** The achievement attained by the students in answering the test items prepared by the teacher that will be carried out in their quarterly grades.
- **Collaborative Teaching Strategy.** It is one form of educational strategy, in which teachers collaborate to create, present, and assess lessons. It frequently comprises two or more teachers working together intentionally to enhance the educational experience for students. Such Collaborative strategy can also be observed during Learning Action Cells, Focused Group Discussions and In-service Trainings.
- **Grade 8 Learners.** These are the learners attending high school education in the Municipality of Malasiqui. They are officially enrolled for the school year 2023 – 2024. They will serve as the main respondents in this research investigation.
- **TLE Teachers.** These are the teachers teaching Technology and Livelihood Education in the Municipality of Malasiqui. They will be part of the respondents in determining the problems encountered in the implementation of the Collaborative teaching strategies and its effectiveness.
- **Malasiqui.** It refers to the locale of the study wherein the teacher is currently teaching and the researcher is presently teaching during the time of the study.
- **School Administrators.** It refers to any official accountable for the supervision of direction of an educational institution or system of an administrative unit this may comprises officials such as college or university presidents, deans, school superintendents, district supervisors, principal and head teachers. In this study, this includes the school heads, master teachers, head teachers, and subject area coordinators.

Chapter 2

Research Methodology

This chapter presented the research design, sources of data, data – gathering instrument, data gathering procedures and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design: This study used the descriptive and developmental method of research to ascertain the utilization of the Collaborative teaching strategies. The sources of data will be taken from the analysis of the responses of the respondents and the result of the test results and responses of the teachers from the given questionnaire and the result of the test taken by the learners.

Based on the analysis of the above results, the researcher developed or introduced Collaborative teaching strategy to improve the teaching performance of the teachers in Technology and Livelihood Education. This inquiry also includes a questionnaire that dealt with the problems encountered by the teachers teaching Technology and Livelihood Education.

It is suitable for circumstances that demand a non-factor-manipulative investigation of differences. To describe the situation as it exists at the time of the investigation, a descriptive approach will be used. The purpose of the study was to identify the factors that led to a particular incident and to describe the nature of the circumstance at the time of the examination. This research plan aimed to be very thorough, Calmorin 2016.

Finally, the data gathered will be treated statistically. It will be presented in tables, computed and the results are compared to standard values.

Sources of Data: This study was conducted in the Municipality of Malasiqui, which comprised of Malasiqui District I, Malasiqui District II-A, and Malasiqui District II-B, during the School Year 2023 – 2024. The respondents are the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the aforementioned districts. Table 1 shows the distribution of teacher – respondents in the school.

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents

School	Number of Teachers	Number of Learners
School A	8	5
School B	8	5
School C	8	5
School D	7	5
School E	7	5
School F	7	5
School G	7	5
School H	7	5
School I	7	5
School J	7	5
School K	7	5
Total	80	60

Instrumentation and Data Collection: Questionnaire will be used in the data - gathering instruments prepared by the researcher. The validated questionnaire for the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers regarding the problems encountered in the implementation of the propose Collaborative teaching strategy. For the learners, a validated test questions were used. This will also use the different Collaborative teaching strategies in order to improve the performance of the respondents. The level of practiced of the Collaborative teaching strategy will also be included in the prepared instrument.

Prior to the start of gathering information and data which will be needed in the present investigation the researcher sought permission from the Office of the Institute of Graduate and Professional Studies in Lyceum Northwestern University for the signing of the permit to conduct, study duly attested by the research-adviser and it will be immediately followed as the researcher seek approval from the office of the Public Schools District Supervisor and Schools Division Superintendent for the conduct of the study, as the researcher needs Technology and Livelihood Education teachers.

The researcher personally administered the distribution of questionnaire for the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers to ensure smooth flow of this research investigation. Consent forms was also be provided for privacy purposes of their responses. The researcher personally makes the rounds in the collection of the test questionnaire in order to ensure 100 percent retrieval.

After retrieval, the data will be tallied, organized and presented in tables for analysis and interpretations.

Tools for Data Analysis

For sub-problem no. 1 on determining the profile of the teacher - respondents, frequency and percentage was used. The formula is:

$$\text{Where: } P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

P = percentage

n = number of particular groups

f = total number of items

For sub – problem number 2, on determining the level of practice of the collaborative teaching strategies for Technology and Livelihood Education it was answered using 3 – Value Likert Scale with the average weighted mean (AWM) and their descriptive ratings as follows;

Scale	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Value
3	2.51 – 3.00	Always Practiced (AP)

2	1.51 – 2.50	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1	1.00 – 1.50	Not Practiced (NP)

For sub-problem number 3, on determining the significant relationship between level of practice and profile of teachers, it was answered using cross tabulation.

For sub-problem number 4 on determining the level of seriousness of the problems encountered as perceived by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers using Collaborative teaching strategy it was answered using a 3-value Likert scale with the average weighted mean as follows:

Scale	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
3	2.84 – 3.00	Serious (S)
2	1.67 – 2.33	Moderately Serious (MS)
1	1.00 – 1.66	Not Serious (NS)

For sub-problem number 5 on the level of performance of Grade 8 learners in Technology and Livelihood Education 8 after utilization of the Collaborative teaching strategies, mean percentage score was used.

$$\text{Mean } (\bar{x}) = \frac{\text{Total Score of Learners}}{\text{Total Number of Takers}}$$

$$\text{MPS} = \frac{\text{Computed Mean } (\bar{x})}{\text{Total Number of Test Items}} \times 100$$

For sub-problem number 6 To determine the significant relationship between the level of practice of collaborative teaching strategies and the level of performance, cross tabulation was utilized.

For sub problem number 7, based from the findings, a development plan was proposed to help to address problems of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers for the adoption and familiarization of the Collaborative teaching strategy and to help improve the performance of the learners.

Ethical Consideration: As a form data-privacy is concern, all actions pertaining to personal information and identity of all involved in this investigation will be kept confidential. This study investigation assures all will keep all responses concealed. As a result, participants will be advised not to include any personally identifiable information in their questionnaire or test material. Their responses will likewise be kept confidential. To preserve each subject's identity, the researcher will keep their information confidential; all information acquired from the study will be coded. No names or other identifying information will be used while discussing or reporting data. The researcher will securely preserve any files and data gathered. Once the data has been completely analyzed, it will be discarded.

Chapter 3

Presentation, Analysis And Interpretation Of Data

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of data gathered through the questionnaire.

The data are composed of the profile of the TLE teachers in terms of highest educational qualification, seminars/trainings attended in TLE, years of teaching experience and field of specialization. Primarily the level of effectiveness of using Collaborative teaching strategies of TLE teachers as perceived by themselves will be analyzed as well as the differences of perception of the respondents. Included in the analysis are the relationship in the level of effectiveness of using Collaborative teaching strategies by the TLE teachers across profile variables and determining also the significant difference on the level of practice and the problems encountered by the TLE teachers in applying the aforementioned strategy. Lastly, the level of performance of the Grade 8 learners.

Profile of the Respondent: Table 2 presents the different profile of the respondents in terms of highest educational qualifications or attainment, field of specialization, years in teaching TLE and, seminars/trainings attended in TLE.

Table 2: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Highest Educational Qualifications**N = 80**

	Frequency	Percentage
Doctorate Degree	9	11.3
Doctorate Unit Earner	10	12.5
Master's Degree	18	22.5
Masters Unit Earner	33	41.3
Bachelor's Degree	10	12.5
Total	80	100.0

Table 2 above reveals that 10 of the respondents are Bachelor's Degree holders, MA Degree unit holders 33, graduates of MA degree are 18, with doctoral degree units 10, and with finished Doctorate Degree Programs with an enumeration of 9. Teachers have met the basic educational qualification. Educational credentials are vital in Collaborative teaching because they ensure that teachers bring a strong foundation of knowledge and skill to the collaborative teaching situation.

Another study that emphasizes just how important education is when it comes to the teaching profession is "Teacher Qualifications and Student Achievement: An Exploratory Analysis," by Linda Darling-Hammond and Gary Sykes 2003. This study checks the connection between the education levels of teachers in relation to their educational preparation regarding the area of competence and student outcomes. The paper appeared in Educational Policy. The study finds that more highly qualified instructors, in terms of their degree level and depth of subject-matter knowledge, tend to have a positive effect on the performance of their students in academic terms. This study validates the importance of funding professional development for teachers as a means of improving classroom instruction and, hence, student achievement.

Table 3: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Field of Specialization**N = 80**

	Frequency	Percentage
Filipino	1	1.3
English	1	1.3
Mathematics	0	0
Science	8	10.0
Social Science	2	2.5
TLE/THE	67	83.8
MAPEH	1	1.3
Values and Religion	0	0
Total	80	100.0

Along the field of specialization, it could be garnered that 67 of the teacher respondents are TLE majors, 8 are Science majors, and 12 are Social Science majors, three (3) are Filipino majors and MAPEH majors, none (0) Mathematics majors, one (1) Filipino, English and MAPEH majors. This finding reveals that there is mismatch that happens in the teaching of the subject. Though, TLE majors were not outnumbered.

Table 4: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Years of Teaching Experience**N = 80**

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
16 years and above	11	13.8
11 – 15 years	26	32.5
6 – 10 years	20	25.0
0 – 5 years	23	28.7
TOTAL	80	100

Table 4 reveals that of the 23 respondents have teaching experiences from 0 – 5 years. Meanwhile, out of the 20 total respondents responded to 6-10 years. Moreover, 26 have teaching experiences from 11 – 15 years, 11 responded for an experience of 16 years and above. Moreover, in a statement by Papay and Kraft (2015), the professional environments in which teachers work can have an effect on the returns to teaching experience, according to the authors of the study "Can Professional Environments in Schools Promote Teacher Development? Explaining Heterogeneity in Returns to Teaching Experience," which was published in Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis. Though the advantages may vary according on the kind of institution, teachers with longer tenure tend to be more effective educators. This simply implies that majority of the teacher respondents are still at the peak of the career delivery services to the clientele. The length of service has a great deal of importance to the growth and status of teacher and that gives effort on her teaching. In addition, after several studies, Kini and Podolsky (2016) came to the conclusion that there was a correlation between teacher effectiveness and student accomplishment. The Learning Policy Institute published their report, "Does Teaching Experience Increase Teacher Effectiveness? A Review of U.S. Research." Experienced educators typically provide better instruction, better classroom management, and a greater capacity to meet the requirements of a wider range of students. These studies show that a teacher's efficacy and the way they affect their students' learning and performance are strongly correlated with their length of teaching experience. With more years of experience, teachers frequently become more adept at organizing the classroom and creating their own teaching tactics.

Table 5: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Seminars/Trainings Attended
N = 80

Number of Relevant Trainings/Seminars Attended	Frequency	Percentage
International Level	0	00.0
National Level	16	20.0
Regional Level	36	45.0
Division Level	17	21.3
District Level	11	13.8
TOTAL	80	100

Along seminars and trainings, it could be gleaned that 16 of the respondents attended National level of seminars and trainings, 36 have attended regional level of trainings, 17 out of 80 attended Division level trainings and 11 for District level training. Meanwhile, none of the respondents attended international level. Teachers' training—which includes both initial classroom preparation and ongoing professional development—has a significant impact on both their success and the academic outcomes of their students. The National Staff Development Council published a report in 2009, Professional Learning in the Learning Profession: A Status Report on Teacher Development in the United States and Abroad, which discusses that continuous professional learning builds teacher effectiveness. Learners excel more in schools where teachers are well-prepared and continuously learning. Teachers can scale lessons based on needs to meet the requirements of diverse learners and employ more effective instructional practices. Desimone, 2009 analyzes the link between instruction and student learning and professional development. She concludes that teaching methods can be enhanced, and student outcomes improved through professional development programs when thoughtfully designed. It was also observed to be so necessary that educators were prepared with regular, relevant training directly matched to the needs in the learning environment.

Level of Practice of Technology and Livelihood Teachers in using Collaborative Teaching Strategies:
Table 6 aptly presents the level of practice of TLE teachers in using Collaborative teaching strategy.

Table 6: Level of Practice of Technology and Livelihood Teachers in using Collaborative Teaching Strategy
N=80

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. The teacher uses Think-Pair-Share peer-to-peer learning and active participation are encouraged by this.	2.16	MP
2. It is the shared responsibility of two or more teachers to organize, teach, and evaluate student. Differentiation, modeling, and peer assistance are all made possible in the classroom.	2.36	MP
3. The use of Jigsaw. This encourages collaborative learning, involvement, and interdependence.	2.48	MP
4. The use Round Robin this method, students sequentially respond to questions or share thoughts one at a time.	2.24	MP
5. Numbered Heads Together Students in a group are given numbers as part of this tactic.	2.41	MP
6. Students work together in pairs or small groups, alternating between the roles of tutee and tutor. Peer tutoring promotes cooperation, clear communication, and a deeper understanding of the material.	2.38	MP
7. To improve student learning both inside and outside of the classroom, schools work in Collaborative with parents, caregivers, and members of the community.	2.40	MP
8. Student participation in community service projects is incorporated into the curriculum.	2.24	MP
9. Working in teams, teachers share best practices, analyze student data, and develop instructional strategies with other educators in their school or district.	2.43	MP
10. Use of Problem-Based Learning which allows collaborative, inquiry-based teaching approach that centers on actual, authentic challenges or scenarios	2.46	MP
Weighted Mean	2.36	MP

2.84 – 3.00 Always Practice (AP) 1.67 – 2.83 Moderately Practice
1.00 – 1.66 Not Practice (NP)

The above-cited table briefly discussed the level of practice of Technology and Livelihood Education in using Collaborative teaching strategy. It could be gleaned that the over-all weighted mean is 2.36 which falls on “Always Practiced”. Teachers that employ Collaborative teaching can learn from each other by sharing innovative strategies and excellent practices. Collaborating can enhance professional growth and elevate the overall quality of teaching (Bacharach, Heck, & Dahlberg, 2010).

When students are exposed to a variety of teaching ideas and methodologies, they become more motivated and engaged. Additionally, greater individualized attention can be given in a classroom with numerous teachers (Gately & Gately, 2001).

It is made simpler to differentiate education in the classroom by many teachers in order to address the unique needs of each student. Even if students have different ability levels and learning preferences, teachers can nevertheless collaborate to provide them focused assistance (Villa & Thousand, 2000).

Teachers that use Collaborative teaching have the opportunity to share creative solutions and best practices and gain knowledge from one another. This Collaborative could result in both professional development and an overall enhancement in the caliber of education (Bacharach, Heck, & Dahlberg, 2010).

Co-teaching is particularly beneficial for inclusive education because it allows general education and special education teachers to work together to serve students with disabilities in a mainstream classroom (Friend, Cook, Hurley-Chamberlain, & Shamberger, 2010).

Students' and teachers' educational experiences are improved by Collaborative teaching. It promotes collaboration, a range of viewpoints, and a welcoming, inclusive learning atmosphere.

The preceding table below discusses the seriousness of the problems encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the implementation of Collaborative teaching strategy.

Significant Relationship Between Level Of Practice And Profile Of Teachers

Table 7: Significant Relationship Between Profile Variables on Educational Attainment and the Level of Practice in Collaborative Teaching Strategy

N = 80

	Always Practice	Moderately Practice	Not Practice	Total
Doctorate Degree	8	1	0	9
Doctorate Degree with units	7	3	0	10
Master's Degree	16	2	2	18
Master's Degree with Units	26	5	2	33
Bachelor's Degree	7	2	0	9
Total	64	8	8	80

According to the cross-tabulation data, there is a significant difference between degrees in terms of the percentage of teachers who always employ collaborative teaching strategies. The degree classes showing a particularly high percentage of engagement are individuals with the highest academic degrees, with 88.9% of those who earned Doctorate degrees and 70% of those who achieved incomplete Doctorate degrees (with units) doing so. Furthermore, 88.9% of those who had earned Bachelor's degrees and 88.9% of those who achieved Master's degrees always employ these strategies, with only a very small percentage in either class employing at a middling rate or not employing the strategies at all. In addition, of all those teachers who had completed some Master's degree, 78.8% employ the strategies and are more likely than all other classes to report that they do not employ.

Table 7.1: Significant Relationship Between Profile Variables on Field of Specialization and the Level of Practice in Collaborative Teaching Strategy

N = 80

	Always Practice	Moderately Practice	Not Practice	Total
Filipino	0	1	0	1
English	0	1	0	1
Mathematics	0	0	0	0
Science	4	3	1	8

Araling panlipunan	0	1	1	2
TLE	46	23	0	67
MAPEH	0	1	0	1
Values/ESP	0	0	0	0
Total	25	50	5	80

The data indicate that TLE is the most specialized of all areas, having the highest percentage of teachers in the category Always Practice, followed by the category Moderately Practice. Likewise, Science shows a category of teachers in the highest group of the Always Practice level, implying that they are highly competent in this area of discipline.

On the other hand, there seemed to be inadequacy in staffing the MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health), Filipino, and English areas as well since there are not too many of these teachers and all at the level of Moderately Practice. The absence of math teachers was a very serious concern and needed urgent consideration.

The cross-tabulation of the data portrays important patterns of teacher proficiency levels in the different subject areas. While TLE emerged with the highest proportion among the subject areas in terms of having teachers with a strong and evenly distributed proficiency across the different practice levels, Science indicated a proportion of highly proficient teachers that is quite respectable.

Table 7.2: Significant Relationship Between Profile Variables on Length of Service and the Level of Practice in Collaborative Teaching Strategy

N = 80

	Always Practice	Moderately Practice	Not Practice	Total
16 years' Experience and above	25	3	4	9
11-15 years' Experience	16	0	2	27
4-10 years' Experience	20	5	2	27
0-3 years' Experience	3	0	0	3
Total	64	8	8	80

The data reflects how practice habits distributed are across four experience levels: 16 years and above, 11-15 years, 4-10 years, and 0-3 years. It shows how many of them "Always Practice," how many of them "Moderately Practice," and how many of them "Not Practice." The "Always Practice" category prevails, and this is especially true for those with 11-15 (24 out of 26) and 4-10 (20 out of 20) years of experience. In contrast, the least experienced category (0-3 years) has a more diversified distribution: three for each practice level, thus indicating that they are not consistent in their practice. A statistical test that can be used to check the independence of practice habits in level of experience is the chi-square test. A significant result (p -value < 0.05) would confirm practice habits to be significantly different among experiences, which on average would mean the highest experience is associated with being more consistent in practice, while the lowest experience is associated with diversification in practice behaviors.

Table 7.3: Significant Relationship Between Profile Variables on Trainings Attended and the Level of Practice in Collaborative Teaching Strategy

N = 80

	Always Practice	Moderately Practice	Not Practice	Total
International Training	0	0	0	0
National Level	14	2	0	16
Regional Training	34	1	1	36
Division Training	15	2	0	17
District Training	10	1	0	11
Total	73	6	1	80

The table shows the practice habits related to the level of training received: International, National, Regional, Division, and District. Notice that there is no entry in the International Training for any of the categories of practice. That most likely means that the data for this intersection of participants is not available or that there were no respondents from International Training. In the category National Training, there are 14 of 16 individuals who "Always Practice" and 2 who "Moderately Practice." There are 34 of 36 individuals in Regional Training who "Always Practice," 1 who "Moderately Practice," and 1 who "Not Practice." There are 15 of 17 individuals in Division Training who "Always Practice" and 2 who "Moderately Practice." There are 10 of 11 individuals in District Training who "Always Practice," and 1 who "Moderately Practice." A chi-square test of independence does find an association between the categories: $p\text{-value} < 0.05$. Since the value is less than 0.05, the level of training actually does influence practice habits. The trend shows that Regional and Division Training are more consistent and National and District more variable in terms of practice. It suggests that International Training should be investigated since no levels from this training are represented in the table.

Table 8: Problems Encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the Implementation of Collaborative Teaching Strategy

N = 80

Problems	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Not equal distribution of work. Resentment and dissatisfaction may result from one partner performing more labor than the other.	2.84	S
2. Teachers have different teaching styles which may affect their teaching relationship or Collaborative	1.79	MS
3. Ineffective partner communication can lead to misconceptions, perplexity, and inefficiencies in lesson design and delivery.	1.92	MS
4. Partners may find it challenging to coordinate their efforts and cooperate toward shared goals if they have different priorities or aspirations.	2.64	S
5. Disparities in teaching ideas or personalities can lead to conflict and impede productive teamwork.	2.08	MS
6. Effective collaboration and planning can be difficult when partners have competing schedules or little time for these activities.	2.28	MS

7. Differential availability to materials, technology, or support personnel can lead to discrepancies in Collaborative teaching.	2.51	S
8. Some teachers may be reluctant to adopt Collaborative teaching because they find it difficult to give up control or because they are not accustomed with collaborative methods.	1.87	MS
9. If teaching methods or styles do not align with the vast range of learning demands of their students, partners may find it difficult to properly engage all of their pupils.	1.99	MS
10. Coordination of assessment protocols and grading criteria can be difficult in Collaborative education, especially if partners have different expectations or standards.	1.83	MS
Weighted Mean	2.19	MS

2.34 – 3.00 Serious (S)

1.67 – 2.33 Moderately Serious (MS)

1.00 – 1.66 Not Serious (NS)

The foregoing table reflected the data gathered on the problems met by the TLE teachers and further stated that the respondents described all the problems as “Moderately Serious” as proven by the overall average weighted mean of 2.19. There are 10 indicators in this table and there are seven indicators which manifested Moderately Serious, these are; Teachers have different teaching styles which may affect their teaching relationship or Collaborative, Ineffective partner communication can lead to misconceptions, perplexity, and inefficiencies in lesson design and delivery, Partners may find it challenging to coordinate their efforts and cooperate toward shared goals if they have different priorities or aspirations, Disparities in teaching ideas or personalities can lead to conflict and impede productive teamwork, Effective collaboration and planning can be difficult when partners have competing schedules or little time for these activities, Some teachers may be reluctant to adopt Collaborative teaching because they find it difficult to give up control or because they are not accustomed with collaborative methods, If teaching methods or styles do not align with the vast range of learning demands of their students, partners may find it difficult to properly engage all of their pupils, Coordination of assessment protocols and grading criteria can be difficult in Collaborative education, especially if partners have different expectations or standards and Effective collaboration and planning can be difficult when partners have competing schedules or little time for these activities.

In addition, there are three indicators that falls on “serious” category, these are; Not equal distribution of work. Resentment and dissatisfaction may result from one partner performing more labor than the other, Differential availability to materials, technology, or support personnel can lead to discrepancies in Collaborative teaching and Differential availability to materials, technology, or support personnel can lead to discrepancies in Collaborative teaching.

Clear communication, clearly defined roles and duties, preparation time, collaborative time, and professional development in co-teaching ways are all necessary to address these problems.

This only suggests that the majority of the serious claims that fit within the serious category were all made within the TLE prospectus. It only notes that the majority of our TLE teachers typically encounter these circumstances. As a result, the government ought to take proactive measures to prevent these issues from getting worse.

Significant Relationship Between the Level of Practice of Collaborative Teaching Strategies and Student Performance: The preceding table discusses the cross tabulations of the academic performance of the grade 8 learners and the level of practice of the TLE teachers.

Table 9: Cross Tabulations of Performance of Students and the TLE teachers' level of Collaborative Teaching Strategies

N=80

	Not Mastered	Not Yet Mastered	Mastered	Highly Mastered	Total
Not Practiced	0	0	0	0	0
Moderately Practiced	0	0	16	2	18
Always Practiced	0	0	52	10	62
Total	0	0	68	12	80

Based from the above-cited table, the data suggests a strong correlation between the frequency of practice and achieving mastery. Individuals who always practice are more likely to reach a higher mastery level compared to those who practice sometimes.

Among those who "Always Practiced", a majority (52 out of 62) reached "Mastered", and a significant portion (10 out of 62) reached "Highly Mastered". Among those who "Moderately Practiced", a smaller but notable portion reached "Highly Mastered" (2 out of 18).

A chi-square test reveals a significant association between practice frequency and skill mastery (p-value < 0.05), indicating that individuals who "Always Practiced" are significantly more likely to achieve higher levels of mastery. This underscores the importance of consistent practice in achieving higher skill proficiency.

Table 10: Performance of the Grade 8 Learners

N = 60

Performance	N	Mean	Mean Percentage	LEARNING LEVEL
	60	37.80	77.92	Mastered

Below 60 - No Mastery
75 to 89 - Mastered

61 to 74 - Not Yet Mastered
90 and above - Highly Mastered

The level of learning of the Grade 8 learners, therefore, could be described as "mastered", based on the above-cited table. This means that Collaborative teaching strategies used by teachers were effective.

According to Smith and Warren (2019), collaborative teaching "encourages varied perspectives on curriculum design, and the sharing of responsibilities among educators, thus, it enhances opportunities for reflective practices." This is to say that an opportunity is given for educators to utilize their combined experience for effective responsiveness to diverse needs with a caring learning environment.

Table 11: Relationship Between Performance and Level of Practice Collaborative Teaching Strategies

	Spearman Rho	Description	Sig
Level of Practice Collaborative Teaching Strategies	-.038	Slight, Almost No Relationship	.741

The level of practiced computer-aided instructional strategies utilized by the teachers was treated as a scaled variable by transforming the data in SPSS using the mean.

The significance level of practiced CAI is 0.741. It is greater than the alpha level of 0.05. This implies that the null hypothesis should be accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the performance of the students and the level of Practiced CAI applied by their teachers

Chapter 4

Summary, Conclusions, And Recommendations

Presented in this chapter is a synopsis of the entire research process undertaken to attain the objectives determining the level of practice of Collaborative teaching strategy by the TLE teachers, and of the inferred conclusions and recommendations for future research.

Summary: This study aimed to determine the level of practice of the Collaborative teaching strategy used by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the Municipality of Malasiqui Schools Division Office I Pangasinan. This study used the descriptive method of research to ascertain the utilization of the Collaborative teaching strategies. The sources of data will be taken from the analysis of the responses of the teachers from the given questionnaire.

Tools that enable the researcher to develop the necessary information and details will be of utmost importance in this research. As this is Descriptive research, the study shall describe existing situations and conditions relative to the study which included a total number of 80 teacher-respondents. The needed data were obtained from the validated questionnaire to measure the level of practice of the Collaborative teaching strategy. Thorough interpretation of the participants' answers shaped the findings of this study. After the gathering of data, the researcher was able to found out the effectiveness of the Collaborative teaching strategies by the TLE teachers.

Findings: The noticeable findings of the study are as follows:

1. Respondents of this investigation are 80 Technology and Livelihood Education teachers who are randomly selected from the Municipality of Malasiqui in the Schools Division Office I of Pangasinan.
2. Data revealed that 33 of the respondents coming from the total of 80 are MA Degree unit holders, 67 are TLE majors, 26 are of 11-15 years of teaching experience, and 36 of them attended regional trainings.
3. The level of practice of using the Collaborative teaching strategy by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers is described as "Moderately Practiced" which means, TLE teachers are using the Collaborative teaching strategies which is a necessary tool in helping and improving the academic performance of the learners as well as the teaching performance of the teachers.
4. This means that there is no relationship between the teachers' profile and their level of practiced collaborative strategies.
5. The problems encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the implementation of Collaborative teaching strategy is described as "Moderately Serious" with an average weighted mean of 2.19.
6. The level of performance of the Grade 8 learners was described as "mastered" which indicates an effective used of the Collaborative teaching strategy.
7. There is a significant relationship between the practice Collaborative teaching strategies and the problems encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the implementation. It garnered a significance of .031, which is less than the alpha level. It means that the null hypothesis should be rejected.
8. A development plan was proposed to help to address problems of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the adoption and familiarization of the Collaborative teaching strategy.

Conclusions: After the whole process of the study, it is concluded that the level of practiced of using Collaborative teaching strategies of TLE teachers in the Municipality of Malasiqui is moderately practice. It is therefore stated based on the findings, that TLE teachers possessed the skills and competencies they need to acquire in the field of teaching their subject area. This manifest further that teachers are equally competent in the field of teaching.

Collaborative teaching must be used to establish a friendly and encouraging learning environment. When teachers with different specialties collaborate, the result is instruction that is more tailored to each student's needs. This is known as co-teaching. When educators collaborate, they may better meet each student's

individual requirements, consider their different learning styles and ability levels, and foster a more positive learning environment.

Teaching effectiveness of teachers really takes a huge part especially in the delivery and execution of instruction. In addition to, the findings of this study leads to the emergent of problems which are encountered by TLE teachers which awakens the schools and at the same time the division to further provide a salient solution in addressing such concerns.

It is also concluded that from the result of the study, that Collaborative teaching strategies is effective based on the increase of performance of the learners and it in improving the skills related to Technology and Livelihood Education of the teachers. This fortifies the idea that involvement of teachers was necessary in the teaching-learning process.

This strategy encourages teachers to share responsibilities, differentiate their instruction, and advance their careers. Teachers can maximize student success by employing Collaborative teaching strategies to foster a collaborative and inclusive learning environment.

Recommendations: The following recommendations are offered, to wit:

1. It is shown in this study that the main subject or respondents used in this investigation are the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers, I thus recommend to the future researcher the participation of other subject teachers or learning area as to the continuity and consistency of result is concern.
2. As part of the local of the study is concern, it is therefor recommended to broaden the scope of research setting as it will also focused on the different congressional districts.
3. With the findings of the study, it is likewise recommended to have a regular focus group discussion on part of the teachers in order to adopt the designed strategy by the researcher for the benefit of other grade level.
4. As part of the research focuse is concern, it is hereby recommended to the future researcher to make another study focusing on the problems encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education.
5. And to make the result of this study more conclusive, it is highly recommended to have further studies and more research regarding the topic to create a more holistic and clear view of the subject matter at hand.

Proposed Development Plan to Address the Identified Problems Relative to the Use of Collaborative Teaching Strategy

Introduction: In the field of education, teaching techniques are essential because they facilitate the systematic dissemination of knowledge, active participation from students, and the accomplishment of learning goals. Since every student has a different learning style, effective teaching tactics make information relevant and approachable for all. In the classroom, educators can foster creativity, teamwork, and critical thinking by implementing a variety of teaching strategies. An encouraging and effective learning atmosphere is another benefit of using effective classroom management techniques. Numerous teaching styles have been linked to improved student results and enhanced student involvement, according to research (Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock, 2001). Therefore, we should embrace this change of our education arena for us to fully feed our young learners the meaningful and extravagant form of learning process as 21st century tells us to do.

This intervention measure is push through because of the evidences which proved the problems encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers in the application of the Collaborative teaching strategy. Moreover, this intervention measure is the answer for the teachers lack of trainings and insufficient learning materials are always on top and perennial problem by most of the teachers.

This proposal may serve as stepping stone to further address such problems of our dear teachers.

Problems Encountered in applying Collaborative Teaching Strategy	Intervention Measures
1. Not equal distribution of work. Resentment and dissatisfaction may result from one partner	- Division Offices, District Office, Schools should engage teachers in

<p>performing more labor than the other.</p>	<p>attending trainings related to Collaborative teaching.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide allocation of funds for the possible team building activities of the teachers’ other means in achieving wholistic Collaborative teaching. - Make connection to all other teachers including the stake holders such as parents and teachers continuously support the Collaborative teaching programs of the Department of Education.
<p>2. Partners may find it challenging to coordinate their efforts and cooperate toward shared goals if they have different priorities or aspirations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All activities should be properly coordinated to all teachers most especially in promoting Collaborative teaching strategy. - Develop a sense of responsibility in shaping good relationship to co-workers in order to promote camaraderie.
<p>3. Different availability to materials, technology, or support personnel can lead to discrepancies in Collaborative teaching.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School administrators should allocate funds for the different projects such laboratory corners, experiential learnings and instructional materials. - Encourage learners and teachers to undergo fund-raising activity through the initiative of Parent-Teacher Association for the purchase of projects other materials intended for TLE. - Embolden all the learners to a livelihood program for the eradication of illiteracy among learners this will eventually benefit our learners a lot - Part of funding is to perform transparency of financial matters to maintain clean records.
<p>4. Lack of student’s interest in their TLE subject</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learners should be involved thoroughly in the teaching-learning process in TLE applying the diversity of learners. - The teachers should be equipped with varied teaching skills and methods in

	<p>order to address the need of the learners.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborative approach in teaching is highly encourage to enjoin every learners in the point of discussion.
<p>5. Inadequacy of facilities and equipment and other instructional materials in the teaching of TLE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers should make ways through making request to the proper authority and other stakeholders to augment such problem. - Tapping the PTA to request funding to build speech laboratories and accomplish reading corners and other instructional materials needed in teaching English - Urge teachers to become resourceful in their own little ways.
<p>6. Lack of trainings related to the area of specialization.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers should attend seminars in the school, district, division, regional, and national level. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers should sometimes use their own pocket to attend seminars which are not sponsored by the school - Conduct Learning Action Cells, District Learning Action Cells in TLE.

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